

Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

CALL	<p>Ministry of University and Research (MUR), Directorate-General for Internationalization and Communication, Notice D.D. 3264 dated 28/12/2021.</p> <p>Mission 4 "Education and Research" - Component 2 "From research to enterprise" - Investment Line 3.1 "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructure", Action 3.1.1 "Creation of new IRs or strengthening of existing ones that contribute to Horizon Europe's Scientific Excellence objectives and networking"</p>
PROJECT TITLE	Humanities and cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
PROJECT ACRONYM	H2IOSC
PROJECT ID	IR0000029
PROJECT WEBSITE	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it
CUP	B63C22000730005
WP	4
OU	OU1 Istituto Opera del Vocabolario - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
DELIVERABLE NUMBER	4.13
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Common semantic framework (interim)
EXPECTED DELIVERY DATE	31.10.2023
ACTUAL DELIVERY DATE	31.12.2023
<p>This project is funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU. The views and opinions expressed are only those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them</p>	

Revisions

Version	Reason	Revised by

Authors

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
CNR-OVI	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	emiliano.deglinnocenti@cnr.it
CNR-OVI	Alessia Spadi	alessia.spadi@cnr.it
CNR-OVI	Francesco Coradeschi	francesco.coradeschi@cnr.it

ABSTRACT:

WP4 is focused on developing interoperability between available **resources** both at a physical level, creating the H2IOSC National Cloud Infrastructure and at a semantic level, by translating the state of knowledge with respect to the resources offered by each RI into a common semantic interdisciplinary and interoperable representation (i.e.: the H2IOSC reference ontology).

WP4 will focus on the alignment (i.e.: collection, cleaning, mapping, and modeling) of resources gathered by the 4 participating RIs. To facilitate the alignment, a common mapping schema will be deployed to support the data transformation process: from the original format(s) towards the H2IOSC reference ontology.

The actual H2IOSC-RO (Reference Ontology) development is meant to create a level of interoperability between resources gathered by RIs, by providing a shared Conceptual Reference Model to represent information coming from heterogeneous sources using a common vision.

The development workflow involves: i) analyzing the state of the art and focusing on common problems related to the management of information provided by the RIs; ii) providing a pipeline of validated actions and guidelines on the assessment and semantization of data; iii) offering practical methods for heterogeneous data integration, including transformation and validation, fostering resources exploitation and reuse.

Table of Contents

LIST OF ACRONYMS.....	4
INTRODUCTION	6
1. COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK.....	7
1.1 WHAT IS A COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK?	7
1.2 CHARACTERISTICS OF A SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK: THE STATE-OF-THE-ART	7
2. STATE OF THE ART: SEMANTIC FRAMEWORKS IN PREVIOUS PROJECTS	8
2.1 CENDARI	8
METADATA SCHEMAS	8
ONTOLOGY	9
VOCABULARIES	ERRORE. IL SEGNALIBRO NON È DEFINITO.
DATA INTEGRATION WORKFLOW	ERRORE. IL SEGNALIBRO NON È DEFINITO.
BEST PRACTICES FOR INTEROPERABILITY	10
2.2 PARTHENOS	10
METADATA SCHEMA	ERRORE. IL SEGNALIBRO NON È DEFINITO.
SEMANTIC MODEL	11
VOCABULARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	11
INFORMATION ARCHITECTURE	11
REFERENCE DATA INTEGRATION WORKFLOW	12
2.3 SSHOC	12
3. INTERRELATION WITH OTHER WPS	14
4. EXPECTED RESULTS	14
4.1 ACTIONS.....	15
5. CONCLUSIONS.....	16
REFERENCES.....	17

LIST OF ACRONYMS

CENDARI	Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure
CIDOC-CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIN-IT	Italian national node of Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN-ERIC)
DARIAH-IT	Italian national node of Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH-ERIC)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
E-RIHS.it	Italian national node of the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
H2IOSC	Humanities and cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OPERAS-IT	Italian national node of Open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities (OPERAS)
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RI	Research Infrastructure
S&CI	Social and Cultural Innovation
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SSHOCro	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud Reference Ontology

INTRODUCTION

The H2IOSC (Humanities and Heritage Open Infrastructure for Social and Cultural Innovation) project aims to establish a federated and inclusive cluster comprising four prominent European Research Infrastructures (RIs) within the ESFRI domain of Social and Cultural Innovation: CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS, and OPERAS. Focused on fostering collaboration among researchers in humanities, language technologies, and cultural heritage, the initiative aims to facilitate the sharing of tools, services, and data.

The main objective of the project is the creation of a national infrastructure for the Humanities and Heritage Sciences in Italy, consolidating the existing national nodes of the participating RIs. Through this integration, H2IOSC endeavors to provide a comprehensive and collaborative platform, enhancing research capabilities and cross-disciplinary cooperation in the specified domains.

Within the H2IOSC project Work Package 4 (WP4): **RIs Nodes and Resources Interoperability**, the mission is to establish a unified approach for managing humanities and cultural heritage materials, addressing familiar challenges arising from the use of multiple digital platforms, tools, and standards:

- High data fragmentation;
- Limited information retrieval;
- Low Integration, isolated contexts;
- Data Overload;
- Limited Accessibility;
- Technological obsolescence;
- Lack of interoperability between systems;
- Data lock-in.

The WP has two primary focuses to achieve interoperability: i) the construction of the physical infrastructure provided by the datacenters, and ii) the implementation of a common semantic framework to promote the FAIRness of the shared data, tools, and other resources. The present document provides an interim report on the latter.

The specific focus is on achieving semantic interoperability, context preservation, and accessibility of contents beyond their original context. WP4 aims to integrate tools for the management of thesauri and vocabularies, ensuring consistent handling of resources within the same environment. A common ontology will be chosen for mapping and modeling data, supported by a mapping schema to facilitate the transformation of resources into a semantic format. This approach enhances project sustainability by enabling the reuse of the mapping schema for resources based on the same standard and accommodating added resources with different standards. Additionally, WP4 aims to create a layer of interoperability between Research Infrastructures (RIs), allowing the integration of records from diverse RIs into a shared vision. This means developing an architecture for common semantic support, including mapping, transformation, maintenance, and updating processes, thereby fostering resource exploitation and an expandable integration environment across participating RIs.

This deliverable provides interim guidelines for common semantic framework implementation within H2IOSC. The framework is designed to help integrate records from individual RIs into a unified and cohesive perspective. The common semantic framework, as a key outcome of this endeavor, is expected to go beyond merely offering a validated pipeline of actions and guidelines for data assessment and semantization. The framework is designed to deliver a practical methodology for the homogenization of data, their subsequent transformation through a triplification process, and validation effectively solving the issues previously described. Through these concerted efforts, the framework aims to enable the efficient utilization of resources with various tools and services,

contributing to a more streamlined and effective data management paradigm within the federated RIs.

This document consists of four parts plus the closing remarks:

- Definition of *Common Semantic Framework*;
- State of the art in development of a common semantic framework for the SSH sector, starting from past projects and experiences;
- The application of the H2IOSC-RO in the interrelation with other WPs;
- Expected results and future actions

1. COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK

1.1 WHAT IS A COMMON SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK?

A *Common Semantic Framework* comprises a set of standards, definitions and workflows allowing information storage and retrieval from multiple, heterogeneous data sources. This framework can be described in terms of two primary sets of processes:

- A pipeline of validated actions and guidelines for the assessment and semantization of data.
- A practical workflow, including a fully working implementation, for the homogenization of data, their transformation (to the defined semantic model) and their validation.

In practice, the framework must provide a robust and scalable data management infrastructure, allowing efficient and accurate information acquisition, processing and storage, and facilitating information retrieval. Given the vast amount of data potentially available, originating from diverse sources and in various formats, having a standardized methodology for effective data handling is a fundamental requirement for the H2IOSC project; the heterogeneity of data in terms of both format and structure means that standardization is a significant challenge.

1.2 CHARACTERISTICS OF A SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK: THE STATE-OF-THE-ART

The common semantic framework to be defined in H2IOSC WP4 must provide a state-of-the-art, robust solution for data management, offering a validated pipeline of actions for data integration, homogenization and validation, as well as enabling resource utilization by tools and services. This framework will be a key element in addressing challenges related to data management efficiently and accurately, allowing optimal use of available resources to achieve high-quality results.

Construction of the framework is critical and non-trivial, but the H2IOSC project can leverage valuable experiences from federated Research Infrastructures (RIs) in prior projects. In this deliverable, we will examine the solutions adopted by previous experiences in the context of Social Sciences and Humanities, including the CENDARI¹, PARTHENOS², and SSHOC projects³. Each of these projects has significantly contributed to data management practices, providing detailed workflows that serve as an excellent foundation for our current activities. This deliverable follows the trajectory of these research experiences, allowing us to build upon their insights and continue our research endeavors. This document will also analyze various tools and services defined in the context of previous projects that promote enhanced interoperability and optimal utilization of available resources.

¹ Cfr.: <http://www.cendari.eu/> (last checked 29.02.2024)

² Cfr.: <http://www.parthenos-project.eu/> (last checked 29.02.2024)

³ Cfr.: <https://sshopencloud.eu/> (last checked 29.02.2024)

Anticipating the conclusions, we note at this point that there are elements present in all the common semantic framework descriptions analyzed in the following. We summarize them here, before going on to a more in-depth description of how each of these elements evolved through the cited projects.

The fundamental elements to build a solid common semantic framework are:

- An Ontology capable of describing all collected data through a unified language
- Standardized Vocabularies supporting the ontology
- A practical Data integration workflow, to convert input data to the shared ontology, store them, and make them accessible

To have an effective semantic framework, the domain experts' contribution is essential, especially in the process of data collection and validation.

2. STATE OF THE ART: SEMANTIC FRAMEWORKS IN PREVIOUS PROJECTS

We will now examine in more detail the data integration and homogenization solutions adopted by other relevant projects in the domain of Social Sciences and Humanities: CENDARI, PARTHENOS, and SSHOC.

2.1 CENDARI

The Collaborative European Digital Archival Research Infrastructure (CENDARI) project (funded by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Program), had the objective of establishing a research infrastructure in the humanities that would integrate archive access, knowledge connection, and research support in two specific areas: First World War studies and Medieval History. One of the anticipated outcomes, particularly from the efforts of CENDARI's Work Package 6 (WP6), was the development of a knowledge framework that combined an integrated metadata strategy and dynamic domain ontologies: this is CENDARI's incarnation of a common semantic framework.

CENDARI's framework has been designed to ensure consistency, coherence, and meaningful connections across the various data, metadata, and ontologies employed within the project, with a specific emphasis on the project's domains.

Key elements of the semantic framework implemented by CENDARI include:

- Metadata standards and Schemas
- A dedicated ontology (based on the general purpose ontology CIDOC-CRM)
- Controlled Vocabularies
- Interoperability/integration layers

Metadata Schemas

The first priority for the WP6 team in CENDARI was to create an *institutional level* metadata schema to enable WP5 to commence work on populating CENDARI with archival descriptions. Subsequently, WP6 work on metadata has focused on reviewing and deciding upon the necessary elements for schemas at the *collection* and *item* level. The work was done in close collaboration with domain experts, that are also the final users of the product. The expected results of this approach were: i) interoperability with archive portals; ii) to satisfy the requirements of researchers.

More in detail, the three-level metadata framework developed by the WP6 team utilizes both new and existing schemas in order to map all the information, as detailed in the table:

Level	Metadata standard
Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encoded Archival Guide (EAG)
Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encoded Archival Description (EAD) • CENDARI Collection Schema (created <i>ad hoc</i>)
Item	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS) • Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) • CENDARI Collection Schema (created <i>ad hoc</i>)

The CENDARI Collection Schema (CCS) was created to allow detailed encoding of collection information, addressing gaps, usage impediments, and future plans. The schema i) enriches the MODS metadata schema at the item level, catering to the detailed requirements of medieval research; ii) integrates TEI elements for manuscript descriptions, lacunae and bibliography; iii) overcomes MODS limitations in capturing intricate codicological features. Consistent cataloging rules prevent redundancy and ensure interoperability between MODS and TEI. Simultaneously, customization aligns elements with CENDARI's needs, adapting the EAG standard for accurate representation, offering precise information tailored to project objectives.

The integrated metadata strategy is a part of the broader CENDARI knowledge framework and is designed to integrate with the designed ontologies.

The division in levels is very important within the CENDARI framework since it also referenced on the ontology, that is actually divided in three types of semantic schemas, according to the metadata available for each level.

Generally, it is recommended to use the established schemas since they are already broadly used and there isn't the risk of knowledge enclosure. Infact, if the use of a schema remains only inside the project it can affect the interoperability objective.

Ontology

CENDARI addressed some key points in the definition of its ontology:

- It should act as a unifying framework
- It should enable alignment of different resources
- It should foster discovery of new knowledge
- It should form the base of the data integration strategy

To address these points, it was decided to adopt the CIDOC-CRM ontology, with minor extensions to adapt the schema to the specific domains' needs. In its final version, CENDARI uses six primary classes:

- Places
- Agents
- Timespans
- Events
- Concepts

The ontology played an essential part of CENDARI's data integration strategy. CIDOC-CRM goes beyond simple hierarchies, including rich interconnections between concepts. It enabled the transformation of a static representation of knowledge into a dynamic and queryable database.

Vocabularies

CENDARI defines *controlled vocabularies* as reference tools comprising standardized terminology and expressions employed to denote concepts, tangible attributes, individuals, locations, occurrences, themes, and various other ideas. Used for the classification, indexing, and retrieval of information, controlled vocabularies facilitate organized management of data. A variety of vocabularies is employed, ranging from concise lists tailored to specific attributes (e.g., reasons for lacunae in manuscripts) to extensive ontologies that amalgamate thousands of terms from various sources (e.g., CENDARI's concept ontology, which integrates LCSH and DDC). All of these are integrated with the overall reference ontology based on CIDOC-CRM.

Best practices for interoperability

In the context of CENDARI, interoperability is achieved through a workflow comprised of a few key passages: i) Crosswalks and transformations enable metadata record creation at the collection level using the CENDARI Collection Schema (CCS); ii) Crosswalks between CCS and Encoded Archival Description (EAD) formats facilitate record transformation; iii) XSLT transformations on the CENDARI metadata page generate EAD from CSS-encoded metadata, ensuring interoperability with various systems; iv) Consistent cataloging rules, particularly at the item level, prevent redundancy between MODS and TEI; v) Domain-specific considerations involve close consultation with specialists, tailoring the schema for research needs, and including elements to enhance historical search and discovery. In particular, this approach aims to ensure interoperability with online archive portals, meeting specific requirements for researchers in the historical domain.

2.2 PARTHENOS

PARTHENOS (Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage Eresearch Networking, Optimization and Synergies) is a project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme with the objective of strengthening the cohesion of research across a number of related fields associated with the humanities. It is worth mentioning that both DARIAH and CLARIN (two out of the four participating RIs in H2IOOSC) actively participated in the project and thus in the development of its semantic framework. PARTHENOS was committed to establishing common standards, coordinating joint activities, and harmonizing policy implementation while pooling services and sharing solutions to address shared challenges. PARTHENOS worked on interdisciplinary research starting from the digitization of data, actively collaborating with thematic research infrastructures and contributing to the development of common data standards and online services. Going beyond coordination, PARTHENOS links and harmonizes initiatives to create a unified platform, streamlining researcher access. By pooling and enhancing these solutions, interlinking existing services, and introducing new tools, PARTHENOS effectively brings an example to bridge gaps in the evolving landscape of digital research.

In this context the Common Semantic Framework is described as a common layer for interoperability of resources coming from different domains that impacts on long term integration and sustainability.

The declared challenge to be addressed is: how to create a layer of interoperability between RIs (in this case DARIAH, CLARIN and other EU-level actors) which will offer an information model that will allow the integration of records from highly diverse individual RIs into a common view that a) allows for the exploitation of resources across the participating member RIs in a way that maintains the epistemic validity of those resources and b) create an environment for a sustainable, expanding integration of these resources according to the needs of researchers and RIs. To address these challenges PARTHENOS proposed a framework with the following elements:

- Information Management architecture and process;
- Semantic Model for representing RI data;
- Minimal metadata proposal for tracking the identity of resources in a common semantic environment.

A registry of resources and their keepers within the environment should also be established.

The CSF should provide support to the implementation of an aggregation service to find all data in one place.

Semantic Model

A semantic framework exploiting an ontological modeling of data structures considered as propositional statements about the world is proposed as the means for creating the data expression which is capable of supporting an agile framework for the representation and management of cross-RI metadata about resources.

The original data remain the prerogative of the individual research communities. The RIs system objective is to map the data on a common ontology that doesn't substitute the original data, it enriches them with a layer of integration as added value. The use of the ontology provides added value. The aim of the model is accessibility of the resources.

The semantic model should be able to represent and connect the process of knowledge generation.

Heterogeneous data must be connected to have common ground. The strategy for connecting and linking the various data includes the Vocabulary Management System and the Reference Data Integration Workflow

Vocabulary Management System

A Vocabulary Management System (VMS) aims to address the heterogeneity of data by classifying it. One of the challenges in organizing diverse resources is the establishment of common points of contact, which involve the use of vocabularies and thesauri.

Information architecture

The solution proposed by the PARTHENOS Project in Deliverable 5.1 is to establish a Communication center to keep the federation updated about the communities that hold data, since research is a work in motion that is continuously enriched.

Data curation: create a research environment to have a communication cycle where researchers are supported and facilitated in terms of efficiency and clarity (transparency) regarding the management of resources in the common framework => Common Information Space => Architecture proposition: components that allow cross-domain registration and curation inside a centralized information service.

Element	Scope
Registry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transforms metadata from Research Infrastructures - Provides a current snapshot of ongoing curation processes - Utilizes a semantic graph to describe relations - Focuses on minimal metadata for resource identification

Content Layer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains both data and metadata about distributed resources mapped from the Registry - Manages all changes to the registry
Indexes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open set of indices generated using the registry for specific retrieval purposes. - Available to users through the query system
Query System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enables hybrid research across registry and community-generated indices
Ris Management System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allows supervision, planning, and tracing of workflows and progress in RI maintenance actions

Reference Data Integration Workflow

The chosen ontology is CIDOC-CRM.

Workflow:

- Identification
- Discovery
- Creation
- Registration
- Integration
- Implementation

From the analysis of the work done for PARTHENOS some common issue have emerged throughout the description of the workflow implementation:

- Heterogeneity of data
- Obsolescence of technical solution to store and manage data
- Contribution of domain experts is necessary to have an in-depth knowledge of resources
- To have high level structures to support resources according to the FAIR principles

2.3 SSHOC

The Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) is a project funded by the EU under the Horizon 2020 framework program gathering 20 partner organizations and their 27 associates in developing the social sciences and humanities area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Whereas in PARTHENOS 2 out of 4 RIs in the Social and Cultural Innovation (S&CI) ESFRI landscape were participating, in SSHOC 3 out of 4 (including DARIAH, CLARIN and E-RIHS) were actively developing the described solutions, making this experience a very close reference for the H2IOSC activities.

SSHOC provided a semantic interoperability framework for incorporating the varied data pertaining to the SSH disciplinary domains and describing their lifecycle. The main component of the SSHOC semantic framework is a dedicated ontology, SSHOCro, based on CIDOC-CRM. Several specific workflows for data integration and validation were also explored for specific use cases relevant to the SSH community.

Ontology and data model

The SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro) proposes an ontological model and RDF Schema to organize knowledge in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC). Developed in the context of the SSHOC project, SSHOCro complements and extends the CIDOC-CRM ontology, the standard reference ontology in SSH research workflows. SSHOCro aims to provide a semantic interoperability

framework for describing the data lifecycle in the SSH disciplinary domains; it emphasizes an event-centric approach, inherited from CIDOC-CRM, for digital provenance models. It enables documenting primary data collection, preliminary and final results, methods, and protocols at each stage of research. The ontology's formalization incorporates provenance metadata, supporting the assessment of meaning, relevance, quality, and possibilities of improvement. SSHOCro facilitates resource discovery, allowing social scientists to publish and share research through data repositories. It serves as a high-level workflow logbook, documenting processes for validation and reuse. The ontology is designed to contribute to a common language for information integration and knowledge networks in cultural heritage and beyond. It acknowledges the diversity of data types and analytical techniques in the social sciences and humanities, emphasizing an iterative research process. SSHOCro's practical use lies in metadata capture schemes for individual projects and mapping, transforming, and integrating data across projects and disciplines, creating interoperable pools of information for reuse.

The development of SSHOCro follows a bottom-up strategy based on actual empirical data and data structures. The ontology focuses on describing research activities in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), their methods, and goals, considering the context in which they occur. The process involved identifying workflow patterns and metadata standards through literature review, workshops, and consultations with SSH data providers.

The ontology development was influenced by extensive research on SSH data repositories, consultation with community members, and consideration of use-cases for validation, so, beside the CIDOC-CRM model it also incorporates information from other ontologies and data models

The model emphasizes the archivist's perspective, focusing on registering information relevant to metadata records, data creation, and availability in a static manner. The goal is not to propose a theory of everything but to model well-understood concepts for data-driven research in SSH.

The development involved identifying high-level generalizations and defining superclasses to maintain simplicity and economy. The ontology was validated through case studies, workshops, and feedback from the SSHOC community.

The ontology relies on existing documented data, with abstractions sought for groups of classes sharing common characteristics. It distinguishes between concepts referring directly to objects/entities and those implying a complex structure mediated by events and relations.

References:

1. D4.18 <https://sshopencloud.eu/d418-sshoc-reference-ontology-beta-version>
2. D4.20 <https://sshopencloud.eu/d420-sshocro-final-version>
3. MS19 <https://sshopencloud.eu/ms19-consultation-ssh-data-producers>

Validation, workflows and tools

The validation process extended to use cases in Heritage Science, Archaeology, and an Open Linked Data Archaeology Case Study. Mappings with other ontologies were performed for alignment.

The workflows proposed in the project are not simple sequences of procedures, with one operation following the other in a linear and predetermined order. Instead, they capture an open process, whereby one can always backtrack to alter bits and pieces of the workflow components, in an iterative manner. This closely reflects the stages involved in information processing in the scientific process - i.e., the iterative, incremental way in which scientific knowledge is produced and verified.

Several SSHOC project deliverables document specific workflows based on relevant use cases which are representative of the data ingestion, validation and semantization process in general. Furthermore, the project defined an open marketplace that collects individual contributions to the overall project effort, along with a requisite specification that tools must align to in order to be included in the marketplace.

References

1. D4.19 <https://sshopencloud.eu/d419-mapping-two-indicative-selected-standards-sshocro-0>
2. D5.16 <https://sshopencloud.eu/d516-report-making-heritage-science-data-fair-open-data-heritage-science-and-archaeology>
3. D7.1 <https://sshopencloud.eu/d71-system-specification-ssh-open-marketplace>
4. MS20 <https://sshopencloud.eu/ms-20-selection-ssh-metadata-standards-mapping-sshocro>
5. MS49 <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/restore> - <https://zenodo.org/records/5217113>

3. INTERRELATION WITH OTHER WPs

The Common Semantic Framework developed in the Work Package 4 is strongly connected to the activities of the other WPs of the H2IOSC project.

Given the work already done in previous projects the H2IOSC federation should capitalize on the results already given by previous experiences the single RIs participated in and reflect on the added value the Federation can provide. The workflow supports a cyclic design of the Common Semantic Framework, with periodical upgrades to be implemented based on novel resources and information acquired in time, to maintain an updated and sustainable model.

- An observatory on resources (standards, ontologies, etc. ...) is to be created within the WP2. This information architecture will provide data about resources, standard, community needs, FAIR assessment, access, and all the information about resources and projects the RIs are involved with.
- WP3 will offer technical evaluation on FAIRness and technological requirements assessment of resources to be mapped.
- The Common Semantic Framework will benefit from the Datacenter physical Infrastructure also built within WP4
- The service will be displayed through the marketplace built by WP5
- The WP6 will provide services that will support the development and maintenance of the Semantic Infrastructure. For example, a service to implement data mapping according to the schemas defined in the workflows.
- The Common Semantic Framework will provide the common semantic layer for interoperability to the pilots developed in WP7
- The diffusion of the Framework will lead to the emergence of training needs for researcher to be addressed in WP8

4. EXPECTED RESULTS

Research Infrastructures are facilitators of the scientific process. They serve as a collaborative platform, bringing together researchers, institutions, and resources. They provide a structured

environment where scientists can collaborate, share ideas, and work collectively on complex problems. This collaborative aspect fosters the exchange of knowledge and expertise. It is important to stress that semantic framework does not seek to replace source data, but to integrate them in a shared environment with the aim of improving the degree of FAIRness of the various resources.

Experience from previous projects in the HS and SSH domains has already identified CIDOC-CRM as the reference ontology for the common data framework. We are going to follow this designation, also to achieve integration with previous experiences. Obviously, the scope of the H2IOSC-RO should be adjusted on the project objectives. Each of the experiences described had its own focus and adopted mapping and modelling solutions based on their needs. H2IOSC-RO aims to offer a layer of interoperability for all resources processed by the RIs, produced within different discipline domains: philology, linguistics, heritage science, social science, open science, etc.

Common issues:

- Necessity to consult domain experts
- Data heterogeneity
- Technological obsolescence
- Data not compliant with declared standards

Common (to all previous examples) elements to be implemented:

- **Ontology:** in the information science community, ontology is often defined broadly as an explicit specification of a conceptualization, embracing various formalized vocabularies like controlled terms, taxonomies, and metadata schemas. This definition encompasses a wide array of relationships between concepts. A more specific perspective, aligned with the W3C, views ontology as formalized vocabularies of terms that define relationships within a particular domain, shared by a community of users. Ontologies play a vital role in the knowledge framework, facilitating resource discovery and connection across various cultural heritage institutions. (cit. CENDARI)
- FAIR principles assessment strategy
- Glossaries and Taxonomies
- Vocabularies

4.1 ACTIONS

- Collect an **explicit list of all data types** we expect we can expect to deal with during the project's lifetime. This both in a broad sense (for instance, images of manuscript, digital editions, experimental datasets, and so on) and, wherever possible, at the specific level of data *formats*, such as JGP, EAD, EAC, TEI, ...;
- Recover the Common Information Space proposition in Parthenos: acquire information about standards from the Landscaping Research Group (WP2) active on monitoring the resources of each RI. Definition of models and schemas for semantic translation from the original standard onto the CIDOC-CRM ontology;
- Ideally, final decisions on the ontology (or ontologies) to adopt should be shared by the 4 IRs and their reference communities. To this purpose, it would be useful to **organize a working group** to discuss the state of the art and find out which tools can be recovered and reused from previous experience and what, if anything, is still missing. Infrastructure-level decisions can then be made transparently for all involved parties. The WG should include technical and

domain experts from each RI to ensure the integration of all types of resources needed by the reference communities;

- Define a cyclic workflow to acquire community needs and utilization of resources. We cannot think that dataset and connected research will stay the same, so we need to check the panorama and the standard to stay up to date. Work with WP1 for management and with WP2 for the observatory on resources to create a sustainable workflow;
- As previous experiences show, CIDOC-CRM (or extension thereof) is the reference standard for the framework ontology. It is important to keep in mind, however, that CIDOC-CRM is a *living standard*, evolving and adapting with time. This is a crucial point in view of H2IOSC aim of **sustainability**: the final workflow for data integration must be designed to accommodate revisions of the ontology, including an evaluation of the resources and effort needed to incorporate such revisions.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the primary objective of the common semantic framework is to enhance the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of shared data, tools, and resources within the project. This goal is achieved through the implementation of mapping and modeling strategies. The framework also incorporates the management of thesauri and vocabularies associated with various disciplinary domains.

The framework will provide comprehensive guidelines for essential processes such as data assessment, semantization, homogenization, transformation, and validation. These guidelines will be continuously updated and improved throughout the project. To ensure compatibility and facilitate resource integration, a common ontology and mapping schema will be selected. This approach not only enhances the project's sustainability but also enables the reuse of mapping schemas for resources adhering to the same standard while accommodating resources with different standards. By employing these strategies, the common semantic framework serves as a crucial tool in promoting effective data management and facilitating collaboration within the project.

The H2IOSC project leverages the knowledge gained from previous initiatives such as CENDARI, PARTHENOS, and SSHOC to establish a robust common semantic framework. These projects have played a crucial role in identifying essential components for constructing a solid framework, which include the definition of reference ontology, standardized vocabularies, and a practical workflow for integrating data. The experiences and methodologies provided by these projects have proven invaluable, serving as a strong basis for the ongoing activities within the H2IOSC project.

Taking a forward-looking perspective, WP4 sets out to establish a sustainable workflow for integrating resources from various RIs. This workflow aims to ensure adaptability in the face of evolving standards and the changing needs of the research community. Drawing upon prior experiences and actively involving domain experts, WP4 endeavors to overcome challenges associated with data heterogeneity, technological obsolescence, and compliance with established standards.

By orchestrating concerted efforts and fostering collaboration with other work packages, the H2IOSC project strives to create a robust and enduring common semantic framework. This framework will enhance research capabilities and foster cooperation across disciplines within the humanities and

heritage sciences. Through these collective endeavors, the project aims to facilitate knowledge exchange, advance research methodologies, and contribute to the progress of the respective fields.

REFERENCES

1. Deliverable developed by the CENDARI WP6 team. «CENDARI D6.3 Guidelines for Ontology Building». July 2014.
http://www.cendari.eu/sites/default/files/CENDARI%20_D6.3%20Guidelines%20for%20Ontology%20Building.pdf
2. Bruseker, George, Martin Doerr, e Maria Theodoridou. «PARTHENOS D5.1 Report on the Common Semantic Framework». Zenodo, 30 aprile 2017.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2668433>.
3. Bruseker, George, Alessia Bardi, Felix Helfer, Eleni Tsoulouha, Elias Tzortzakakis, e Ksenia Zaytseva. «PARTHENOS D5.7 Report on the Integration of Reference Resources». Zenodo, 31 gennaio 2019. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2671619>.
4. Bekiari, Chryssoula, Athina Kritsotaki, e Eleni Tsoulouha. «SSHOC D4.18 SSHOC Reference Ontology (beta Version)». Zenodo, 26 marzo 2020.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3744861>.
5. Chryssoula Bekiari, Eleni Tsoulouha, e Ariane Neroulidis. «MS19 Consultation with SSH Data Producers». Zenodo, 30 giugno 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5914407>.
6. Eleni Tsoulouha, Athina Kritsotaki, Chryssoula Bekiari, e Maria Theodoridou. «D4.19 Mapping of Two Indicative Selected Standards to the Sshocro». Zenodo, 31 gennaio 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4457496>.
7. Chryssoula Bekiari, Athina Kritsotaki, Eleni Tsoulouha, e Maria Theodoridou. «D4.20 Sshocro (final Version)». Zenodo, 27 aprile 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6771757>.
8. Joseph Padfield, Orla Delaney, e Anna Amat Alberti. «D5.16 Report on Making Heritage Science Data FAIR (open Data in Heritage Science and Archaeology)». Zenodo, 30 aprile 2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6779595>.
9. Laure Barbot, Yoan Moranville, Frank Fischer, Clara Petitfils, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, Tomasz Parkoła, Philipp Wieder, e Sotiris Karampatakis. «SSHOC D7.1 System Specification - SSH Open Marketplace». Zenodo, 19 novembre 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558302>.
10. Chryssoula Bekiari, Eleni Tsoulouha, Athina Kritsotaki, Maurizio Sanesi, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, e Ariane Neroulidis. «MS 20 Selection of SSH Metadata Standards for Mapping to Sshocro». Zenodo, 24 giugno 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4582018>.
11. Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Carmen Di Meo, Francesco Coradeschi, Maurizio Sanesi, Elisa Brunoni, Athina Kritsotaki, e Eleni Tsoulouha. «MS49 Heritage Science and Humanities Pilot Alpha Release». Zenodo, 31 marzo 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5217113>.